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with International Participation

CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS AND TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE

devoted to
40th anniversary of the
Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry
of NAS of Ukraine

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Тези доповідей Всеукраїнської конференції з міжнародною участю “Хімія, фізика і технологія поверхні”, присвяченій 40-річчю з дня заснування Інституту хімії поверхні ім. О.О. Чуйка НАН України – Київ, 2026. – 290 с.

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Збірник містить тези доповідей, які було представлено на конференції. Тематика конференції: теорія хімічної будови та реакційна здатність поверхні твердих тіл; фізико-хімія поверхневих та міжфазних явищ; хімія, фізика та технологія наноматеріалів; медико-біологічні та біохімічні аспекти вивчення наноматеріалів. Тези доповідей подано в авторській редакції.

The Book contains abstracts of the Conference presentations. The Conference topics: theory of chemical structure and reactivity of solid surfaces; physical chemistry of surface and interfacial phenomena; chemistry, physics and technology of nanomaterials; medical, biological and biochemical aspects of investigation of nanomaterials. The abstracts are published in the author's edition.

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Relationship between rotation speed and phase composition of organic-inorganic perovskite films

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Organic-inorganic perovskites are one of the most intensively studied classes of functional materials due to the combination of high light absorption coefficients, carrier diffusion lengths, and the possibility of forming high-quality films from solution. Such properties open up broad prospects for their use in photonics and optoelectronics, in particular in new-generation solar cells. One of the most common methods for forming perovskite films is the spin-coating, which allows controlling the morphology, thickness, and crystal structure of the layer by changing the technological parameters. Changing the rotation speed can lead to the formation of homogeneous, well-crystallized films, as well as to the appearance of defects, porosity, or residual phases of precursors.

The work aims to study the effect of substrate rotation speed on the structural properties of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite films obtained by spin-coating from a solution in DMSO at the ratios $\text{PbI}_2:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I} = 1:1-1:3$. Deposition was performed at 20 and 40 rpm with subsequent annealing at 160, 190, and 205 °C, respectively – temperatures optimal for the formation of single-phase perovskite.

It was shown that at a composition of 1:1, a multiphase system is formed in the films, which includes $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_8$, $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ and $\text{PbI}_2\cdot\text{DMSO}$. Increasing the substrate rotation speed to 40 rpm increases the content of intermediate solvate phases and reduces the perovskite content. For films obtained with an excess of the organic component (1:2 and 1:3) at temperatures of 190 °C and 205 °C, respectively, a single-phase perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ is formed regardless of the rotation speed.

It is shown that increasing the substrate rotation speed from 20 to 40 rpm in all studied systems results in thinner films. It is established that the rotation speed's effect on phase composition depends on the system's stoichiometry: for the 1:1 composition, higher speeds promote the stabilization of intermediate solvate phases, while for the 1:2 and 1:3 systems, a change in rotation speed does not produce additional phases.

Thus, the substrate rotation speed is a universal parameter that determines film thickness and the degree of perovskite phase formation, and its effect on the phase composition is mediated by factors such as the reagent ratio and the heat-treatment temperature. Optimization of these parameters allows you to control the structural characteristics of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ films.